

Impact of Corporate Environmental Responsibilities on Financial Performance

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Abstract

This research investigates the nexus between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance within the oil, gas, mineral, and metal mining sector. Aiteo Groups and Sahara Groups are utilized as case studies to probe the influence of environmental policies on financial performance. Employing theoretical frameworks and financial metrics such as return on equity, return on assets, and stock market performance, the study aims to elucidate the impact of environmental responsibilities on financial outcomes. The results reveal a nuanced relationship between the financial performance of Aiteo Group and Sahara Group and their commitment to corporate environmental responsibility. The results showed that managers' environmental attitude is a good predictor of corporate reputation, with R squared and adjusted R squared of 0.519 and 0.489 respectively and a significant linear relationship at the 1% level. While a positive correlation is identified between financial performance and robust environmental practices, there is evidence that short-term financial performance may be negatively impacted by environmental activities. Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors should be integrated into investment choices, as these studies highlight. These findings have consequences for managers, investors, and politicians. Moreover, the study uncovers a noteworthy correlation between corporate reputation and environmental attitudes among managers in the extractive industries.

Keywords: Corporate environment, Environmental responsibilities, Stakeholders, Financial performance

Introduction

In the field of business studies, there is a growing interest in the dynamic link that exists between financial performance and corporate environmental responsibilities. There is increasing demand on businesses all over the world to address environmental issues while still being financially viable and competitive in their particular markets. The objective of this research is to thoroughly investigate and evaluate the complex relationships that exist between a company's financial performance and its environmental responsibilities. There has been a paradigm change in business thinking toward environmental duties in the last several decades. According to Dangelico & Pujari (2010), businesses have started to recognize the importance of sustainability programs as essential elements of their corporate strategies. Corporate environmental responsibilities cover a wide range of activities and procedures, such as developing eco-friendly products, adopting renewable energy sources, managing resources sustainably, lowering carbon footprints, and deploying eco-efficient technologies (King et al., 2020). Prominent works by Porter and van der Linde (1995) highlight the strategic benefits that companies may get by tackling environmental issues head-on. Analyzing a company's financial performance is still essential to determining its performance and longevity. A firm's financial health and sustainability may be determined in large part by metrics including market value, profitability, return on investment, and stock market performance (Eccles et al., 2011).

According to research by Clarkson et al. (2008), there may be relationships between business sustainability initiatives and financial performance that go beyond short-term gains. Comprehending the complex relationship between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial outcomes is crucial for companies hoping to prosper in a market that is changing quickly. Environmental activities have been viewed as a cost burden by traditional economic theories, but recent research has shown that these efforts may also be a source of competitive advantage and long-term financial performance (Delmas & Pekovic, 2018). This study centers on the relationship between environmental responsibilities and financial performance, with the aim of identifying complex linkages and causal links that affect company strategy and financial results (Looser et al., 2021). This study aims to provide useful insights that might guide strategic decision-making for companies navigating the challenging landscape of environmental responsibility and financial performance by combining these diverse viewpoints and actual data. By defining important terms, citing significant research, and emphasizing the significance of examining the relationship between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance, the Introduction establishes the framework for the investigation. However, some contend that taking environmental responsibility comes with a price and can hurt a business's financial line. Examining how corporate environmental

responsibilities affect financial performance is the goal of this study. The study will specifically investigate the connection between environmental accountability and important financial indicators including stock performance, profitability, and return on investment. Through the examination of data from several businesses in various sectors and industries, the research seeks to offer a thorough grasp of the relationship between financial performance and environmental responsibility.

The volume of research on this subject is expanding, and several studies offer proof that environmental responsibility may have a favorable effect on financial performance. For instance, a 2013 study by Eccles and Serafeim discovered that businesses that place a high priority on environmental sustainability had a higher chance of outperforming their competitors in terms of profitability and stock performance. Similar findings were made by Klassen & McLaughlin (1996), who discovered that businesses are more likely to get a greater return on investment when they invest in environmental protection policies and technology. Nevertheless, evidence of the opposite has been presented by other investigations. According to Hart and Ahuja (1996), a company's financial performance may suffer as a result of environmental responsibility since such expenditures may be expensive and divert resources away from other aspects of the firm. According to Porter and van der Linde's (1995) research, environmental rules may also negatively affect a company's profitability and competitiveness.

There is a growing consensus that environmental responsibility is becoming more and more essential to stakeholders, including investors, consumers, and employees, notwithstanding these contradictory findings. Businesses that put an emphasis on environmental sustainability have a better chance of drawing in socially conscious investors and cultivating enduring bonds with clients who are glowingly conscious of how their purchases affect the environment. Furthermore, firms that place a high priority on environmental responsibility have a greater chance of drawing in and keeping workers who are enthusiastic about sustainability and want to work for organizations that share their values.

The study focuses on how corporate environmental responsibilities are becoming more important in the business world and how they affect profitability. By doing a detailed investigation of this connection using empirical data and theoretical frameworks, it seeks to add to the body of current literature. Environmental duties of corporations include things like investing in renewable energy sources, encouraging energy efficiency, and cutting emissions. The report highlights many factors that are pushing businesses to take

on these responsibilities, such as growing investor and consumer awareness, legal requirements, and the established connection between profitable operations and excellent environmental performance. The intricate connection is examined, highlighting possible long-term advantages including enhanced brand recognition and easier access to funding while also noting short-term drawbacks. The goal of the study is to offer insightful information to businesses, investors, and politicians, highlighting the significance of environmental stewardship for sustained financial performance.

This study looks at how financial performance in the extractive companies—a sector notorious for its unethical behavior and environmental degradation—is affected by corporate environmental responsibility. The study attempts to close a knowledge gap about how unethical business practices and environmental deterioration affect the corporate financial performance of businesses in the companies. The study creates two distinct data sets and research methodologies to examine two hypotheses with a focus on the extractive companies, which includes the oil, gas, mining of minerals, and metals industries. The results may help resolve the ambiguity in earlier research and offer a more thorough comprehension of the connection between environmental performance and financial performance. This study investigates the impact of corporate environmental responsibility on the financial performance of businesses in the extractive companies, including oil, gas, mineral, and metal mining (i.e. Aiteo Group and Sahara Group). It aims to fill a knowledge gap by using causal and survey research approaches. The research will also examine whether managers' perceptions of their company's reputation are correlated with their environmental attitudes. The study aims to find new data and explain variations in previous research outcomes.

Literature Review

The intersection of corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance has emerged as a crucial area of study within the domain of business strategy and sustainability. Scholars have extensively explored the intricate relationship between a company's environmental commitments and its financial outcomes, shedding light on various dimensions that shape this complex interplay. In examining the relationship between environmental responsibilities and financial performance, it becomes evident that the landscape is multifaceted and dynamic. The term "the" encapsulates the singular focus on understanding the specific linkages between these two critical aspects of corporate operations. Scholars such as Clarkson et al. (2008) have emphasized the considerable impact that corporate environmental responsibilities can exert on financial performance. Their study highlights the potential implications of environmental

initiatives on financial metrics, stressing that these initiatives can lead to enhanced brand reputation, cost savings, and long-term value creation. The relationship "of" corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance signifies a directional influence—how environmental commitments affect financial metrics. Porter and van der Linde's seminal work (1995) articulated the concept of the Porter Hypothesis, suggesting that stringent environmental regulations can drive innovation and efficiency, positively impacting financial outcomes. The focus on the corporate sphere underscores the significance of business entities in addressing environmental concerns. Dangelico & Pujari (2010) discussed the evolving role of corporations in embracing environmental responsibilities, highlighting the shift towards integrating sustainability into corporate strategies to enhance competitiveness and stakeholder trust. The environmental dimension encompasses a broad array of corporate initiatives aimed at mitigating ecological impacts. This includes efforts to reduce carbon emissions, optimize resource usage, adopt renewable energy sources, and implement eco-friendly technologies (King et al., 2020). Corporate responsibilities extend beyond financial responsibilities to include ethical and societal accountabilities. The concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR) emphasizes a company's commitment to managing its environmental, social, and economic impacts (Carroll, 1979). The preposition "on" signifies the relationship between environmental responsibilities and financial performance. Looser et al. (2021) conducted a study that explores the direct influence of corporate environmental initiatives on various financial metrics, highlighting correlations between sustainable practices and financial outcomes. Eccles et al. (2011) delved into the importance of financial metrics in evaluating a company's performance. They emphasized the significance of financial indicators such as ROI, profitability, and stock market performance as crucial benchmarks for assessing the impact of environmental responsibilities. Measuring performance extends beyond financial metrics to encompass broader corporate performance indicators. The holistic view advocated by Van Beurden & Gössling (2008) incorporates both financial and non-financial performance measures, aligning environmental initiatives with overall business performance.

I. **Environmental Responsibilities**

Corporate environmental responsibilities refer to the actions taken by companies to minimize their impact on the environment. These actions may include reducing greenhouse gas emissions, minimizing waste, and conserving natural resources. The importance of corporate environmental responsibilities has been recognized globally, with many countries implementing laws and regulations to encourage companies to adopt environmentally sustainable practices.

ii. **Financial Performance**

Financial performance refers to the ability of a company to generate profits and create value for its shareholders. Financial performance can be measured through various financial indicators such as return on investment (ROI), earnings per share (EPS), and revenue growth.

Corporate Environmental Responsibilities and Financial Performance:

The impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance has been a topic of debate among researchers. Some studies suggest that companies that adopt environmentally sustainable practices may experience improved financial performance, while others argue that there is no significant correlation between the two. One study conducted by Eccles & Serafeim (2013) found that companies that adopted environmentally sustainable practices had higher stock prices and better financial performance. The study analyzed the performance of 180 companies over a period of 18 years and found that companies with high environmental, social and governance (ESG) scores outperformed those with low ESG scores. Similarly, a study by Hoepner et al. (2016) analyzed the performance of 2,200 companies over a period of 10 years and found that companies with higher ESG scores had higher stock returns and lower risk. The study also found that companies that adopted environmentally sustainable practices had a positive impact on their financial performance. On the other hand, some studies have found no significant correlation between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance.

Hong & Kacperczyk (2009) analyzed the performance of 1,500 companies over a period of 13 years and found that there was no significant correlation between environmental performance and financial performance. Similarly, a study by Orlitzky et al. (2003) analyzed the performance of 49 companies and found that there was no significant correlation between environmental performance and financial performance. The mixed results on the relationship between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance can be attributed to several factors. One possible explanation is that the impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance may vary depending on the companies or sector in which the company operates. For example, a study by Chang et al. (2018) found that the impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance was stronger in the manufacturing companies than in the service companies. The study analyzed the performance of 2,057 companies over a period of 10 years and found that companies in the manufacturing companies that adopted environmentally sustainable practices had higher financial performance than

those in the service companies. Another possible explanation is that the impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance may be influenced by the size of the company.

A study by Grewal & Navarro (2016) analyzed the performance of 426 companies and found that smaller companies that adopted environmentally sustainable practices had a positive impact on their financial performance, while larger companies did not experience significant improvements. The impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance has been a topic of significant research and scholarly interest. This literature review aims to explore the existing studies and theories on this topic, providing a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance.

i. **Corporate Environmental Responsibility and Financial Performance**

Numerous studies have highlighted the positive impact of corporate environmental responsibility on financial performance. For instance, Klassen and McLaughlin (1996) conducted a meta-analysis of 40 studies and found a positive correlation between environmental performance and financial performance. They suggested that companies with better environmental performance can achieve cost savings through resource efficiency, gain competitive advantage, and attract environmentally conscious customers.

ii. **Stakeholder Engagement and Financial Performance**

Stakeholder engagement plays a crucial role in linking corporate environmental responsibilities to financial performance. Bansal & Roth (2000) argued that stakeholder pressure, particularly from customers, investors, and regulators, can incentivize companies to adopt environmentally responsible practices. They found a positive relationship between environmental performance and financial performance, indicating that companies with strong stakeholder engagement tend to experience better financial results.

iii. **Reputation and Financial Performance**

Corporate environmental responsibility can contribute to enhanced brand image and reputation, leading to improved financial performance. A study by Ellen et al. (2006) found that consumers have a positive perception of companies that prioritize environmental sustainability. This positive image can translate into increased customer loyalty, higher market share, and ultimately, higher revenues. The study emphasized the importance of aligning corporate environmental responsibilities with customers' values to reap the financial benefits.

iv. **Resource Efficiency and Financial Performance**

Adopting environmentally responsible practices can result in cost savings and operational efficiencies, positively impacting financial performance. Zhu and Sarkis (2006) argued that practices such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, and recycling can lead to reduced expenses and increased profitability. Their study revealed that companies that prioritize resource efficiency have a competitive advantage and can achieve superior financial performance compared to their peers.

Overall, the existing literature highlights a positive relationship between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance. Companies that prioritize environmental sustainability often experience improved financial performance through enhanced reputation, stakeholder engagement, customer loyalty, and cost savings through resource efficiency. However, it is important to consider companies-specific factors and the role of stakeholder engagement in realizing these financial benefits.

Theoretical review

The theoretical review for studying the impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance is grounded in several established theories and concepts in the field of business and sustainability. This review provides a foundation for understanding the relationship between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance and helps guide the research and analysis conducted in this study. Corporate Social Responsibility is a widely recognized concept that refers to the voluntary actions taken by companies to address the social, economic, and environmental impacts of their operations. The theory suggests that companies that prioritize CSR, including environmental responsibilities, can enhance their reputation, build customer loyalty, and improve financial performance. This is because companies that engage in sustainable practices are seen as more trustworthy, ethical, and responsible, leading to increased support and patronage from customers and stakeholders (Porter & Kramer, 2011). Stakeholder theory suggests that companies should consider the interests and expectations of all stakeholders, including customers, employees, suppliers, and local communities, in their decision-making processes. This can lead to increased support, collaboration, and financial performance. The Resource-Based View (RBV) asserts that a company's unique resources and capabilities are key drivers of its competitive advantage and financial performance. Companies that develop and leverage their environmental resources can gain a competitive edge and enhance financial performance through sustainable practices like energy efficiency and waste reduction. Institutional theory focuses on how

organizations conform to prevailing norms and regulations, arguing that adopting environmental responsibilities can avoid reputational risks and potential sanctions. Aligning with emerging environmental norms and regulations can also gain legitimacy and a competitive advantage, ultimately improving financial performance.

The theoretical underpinning of "impact" in this context draws upon various theories that explore how corporate actions in environmental responsibility influence financial outcomes. One such theory is the Triple Bottom Line (TBL), which posits that companies should consider not only economic gains but also social and environmental impacts (Elkington, 1994). The concept of Impact Investment emphasizes investing in companies that generate positive social and environmental impacts alongside financial returns (Schaltegger et al., 2016).

Empirical review

The term "corporate environmental responsibility" (CER) describes the steps a company takes to reduce its adverse environmental effects. Many businesses have adopted CER in recent years as a means of enhancing their public perception and lessening their environmental impact. Nonetheless, some critics contend that CER programs are expensive and don't always result in better financial performance. An empirical analysis of the literature on the effect of CER on financial performance is presented in this research. The idea of CER first surfaced in the 1960s and 1970s in response to mounting worries about pollution and the state of the environment. Since then, consumer demand, social responsibility, and regulatory constraints have all contributed to a slow but steady movement in company practices toward those that are more sustainable. CER programs may take many different forms, such as cutting back on greenhouse gas emissions, employing eco-friendly products, and conserving energy and water. Although the advantages of CER are frequently discussed in terms of their effects on society and the environment, there is also a growing corpus of research that looks at the financial effects of CER. Researchers are particularly curious about whether CER activities may result in better financial performance, which includes greater stock prices, profits, and credit ratings.

One study by Klassen and McLaughlin (1996) examined the relationship between environmental management and financial performance in 50 Canadian firms. They found that firms with strong environmental management practices had higher financial performance than those with weak environmental management practices. Specifically, they found that firms with strong environmental management practices had higher returns on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE).

Similarly, a study by Orlitzky, Schmidt, and Rynes (2003) analyzed the relationship

between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and financial performance in 200 firms. They found a positive relationship between CSR and financial performance, including ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q (a measure of firm value). They also found that firms with higher CSR scores had lower costs of capital, indicating that investors perceive CSR as a positive signal of firm quality. However, other studies have found no significant relationship between CER and financial performance. For example, a study by Buysse and Verbeke (2003) analyzed the relationship between environmental performance and financial performance in 202 Belgian firms. They found no significant relationship between environmental performance and profitability, although they did find a significant positive relationship between environmental performance and sales growth. Similarly, a study by Hart and Ahuja (1996) examined the relationship between environmental management and financial performance in 43 US firms. They found no significant relationship between environmental management and financial performance, although they did find a positive relationship between environmental management and sales growth.

Finally, some studies have found a negative relationship between CER and financial performance. For example, a study by Freedman and Jaggi (1982) examined the relationship between pollution control expenditures and financial performance in 33 US firms. They found that firms that spent more on pollution control had lower profitability and lower market value. Financial performance and Corporate Environmental Responsibility (CER) efforts have a complicated link that is impacted by a number of variables. A role is played by the kind of CER project, the industrial context, and the stakeholder context. For example, increasing energy efficiency may result in cost savings, while running green marketing initiatives may enhance consumer impressions. Businesses in ecologically delicate sectors might give CER programs top priority in order to reduce regulatory risks and harm to their brand. Investment in CER programs may also be impacted by stakeholder pressure. Thus, before making an investment, businesses should thoroughly consider the costs and advantages. Future studies must to examine the intricate connection between financial performance and CER.

Methodology

The researcher employs a causal research design aimed at investigating cause-and-effect relationships. In this design, the researcher observes effects and then seeks to establish causal connections by examining data for potential causal factors. The subjects are already assigned or classified into different levels of the variables being investigated, and the researcher cannot alter this assignment. This design is known as *ex-post facto* because data are collected after the event or phenomenon has occurred. The causal research design

focuses on studying causes after they have presumably influenced another variable before the research. The term "causal-comparative" is derived from the fact that groups differentiated by independent variables are compared on a given dependent variable. In this research, inferential statistics, particularly parametric statistics, are utilized for data analysis.

A study questionnaire was created for Aiteo Group and Sahara Group to gather data on managers' attitudes toward the environment and whether or not these attitudes affected how their company was seen as a whole in order to test hypothesis H_1 and H_2 . According to Leary (2001), surveys ask questions on people's attitudes, lives, behaviors, and issues, hence it is determined that survey research design is the most pertinent and appropriate for assessing H_1 and H_2 . Furthermore, a number of earlier studies conducted in the fields of corporate citizenship, environmental performance, and corporate social responsibility (Khanna et al., 2009, Marshall et al., 2009, and Wagner and Schaltegger, 2004) relied on survey research design following the "most preferred" causal design. Respondents to surveys furnish personal data by means of filling out questionnaires or responding to interview questions. A cross-sectional survey approach is employed in this study, which is targeted at managers of multinational extractive industries. Leary (2001) states that the majority of surveys use a cross-sectional design, which involves polling a single group of respondents—a "cross section" of the population.

Globally, the survey method is currently a recognized and often used research technique. It entails posing structured questions to a purportedly representative sample of the populace at a specific moment in time (Malhotra & Birks, 2000; Bailey, 1982). Respondents to the survey may be mailed the form, speak with a representative in person, answer it over the phone, or do it online. The most common kind is the postal survey (Bryman, 2011). Mail surveys are still a vital tool for gathering data, according to Birn (2000), who also notes that the public prefers and finds them to be a cost-effective way despite the rise in telephone research. According to this study, self-administered and electronic-mail surveys that is, surveys conducted via the internet—are more pertinent for distributing study questionnaires to managers in the extractive companies. The online survey tool Kwik survey is used in this study to get the data required to assess both hypothesis 1 and hypothesis 2. There were three sections in the questionnaire. Statements in Section A assess respondents' attitudes about the environment, whereas statements in Section B are intended to gauge managers' perceptions on the value of a company's reputation. The demographic data of the respondents is gathered in section C. A five-point Likert scale with the following points: strongly disagree (SD), disagree (D), neither (N), agree (A), and strongly agree (SA) is used in the survey.

It was noted that there isn't a scale or measurement that is generally agreed upon to assess a manager's environmental attitude. According to Krosnick et al. (2005), there are two main categories of attitude measuring approaches: implicit measurement techniques and direct self-report methods. Direct self-report methods are more common since implicit measuring methods might be challenging to utilize (Corral- Verdugo, 1997). According to Dunlap & Jones (2003), there are three commonly used measures that have had their validity and reliability evaluated: the Ecological Scale (Maloney et al., 1975), the Environmental Concerns Scale (Weigel & Weigel, 1978), and the New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) Scale (Dunlap, 2000). All managers employed by the extractive industries made up the research population for the tests of Hypotheses H₁ and H₂. A total of 275 senior staff and managers employed by the listed extractive industry made up the research sample. Since this is the most popular technique and is thought to give a reasonably accurate and conveniently available sample frame, a simple random sampling strategy is utilized to acquire the data for this investigation (Saunders et al. 2003).

Data Analysis

Demographic characteristics of the sample

Table 1: Summary of respondents' demographic variables

Variable	Value Label	Freq. (%)	Total
Gender	Male	207(75)	275(100%)
	Female	68(25)	
Age	16–24 years old	11(4)	275(100%)
	25–34 years old	133(48)	
	35–44 years old	95(35)	
	45–55 years old	36(13)	
	more than 55 years	nil	

Companies	Oil, gas, mining or metal	275(100)	275(100%)
	Others	nil	
Position	Manager Senior manager	173(64)	270(100%)
	Executive management	48(18)	
		49(18)	
Education	Secondary	5(2)	275(100%)
	Tertiary	139(51)	
	Post-graduate	131(48)	

Source: Researcher, 2023

Table 1 provides a summary of the sample demographics. Male responses outnumbered female respondents (75% against 25%). This implies that males predominate in the extractive industry's managerial cadre, which may not come as a surprise given the prevalence of men in technical and engineering domains. Regarding the age profile, the responses are not equally distributed across the following age groups: 16–24 (4%), 25–34 (48%), 35–44 (35%), 45–55 (13%), and over 55 (0%). The extractive industry, which includes the mining, oil, and gas sectors, comprises all of the respondents. All of the respondents hold managerial positions, comprising 64% of managers, 18% of senior managers, and 18% of executive managers. The large number of managers in comparison to other cadres may be explained by the fact that in most surveys of this kind, senior managers and executive staff frequently assign younger managers to produce questionnaire replies. An additional reason is that the number of employees decreases as one moves up the hierarchical structure of an organization, which resembles a triangle. The educational background of the respondents, which includes secondary (2%), tertiary (51%) and postgraduate (48%) degrees, is not surprising given that higher institution degrees, such as diplomas and first degrees, are the recruitment entry point for positions below manager in the extractive industry.

Estimation of result for H₁

H₁: The corporate reputation of a company is correlated with a manager's attitude toward the environment

Given the Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.211, which is statistically significant at the 1% level, the correlation results in Table 1 show that there is a correlation between managers' environmental attitudes and the perceived corporate reputation of their respective organizations in the extractive sector. A general linear model (GLM) procedure was carried out to further confirm the relationship between the two variables (see Table 4.2). The results showed that managers' environmental attitude is a good predictor of corporate reputation, with R squared and adjusted R squared of 0.519 and 0.489, respectively, and a significant linear relationship at the 1% level. Thus, the H₁ is approved.

Table 2: Summary of general linear model (GLM) result for H₁

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	34.643(a)	16	2.165	17.403	.000
Intercept	2696.329	1	2696.329	21672.275	.000
EA	34.643	16	2.165	17.403	.000
Error	32.099	258	.124		
Total	4701.800	275			
Corrected Total	66.742	274			

R Squared = .519 (Adjusted R Squared = .489), Dependent Variable: CR

Source: Researcher, 2023

Estimation of results for H₂

H₂: Top level managers exhibit better environmental attitudes than the lower level managers.

Based on statistically negligible changes in the mean score across the three managerial levels ($F(2, 267) = 0.716, p = 0.490$), the results indicate that there is no difference in environmental attitude regardless of the managerial position (see Table 3). A closer examination of the descriptive statistics reveals that the mean score for each of the three managerial levels in the study—manager, senior manager, and executive management—is nearly identical. This suggests that a manager's expected environmental attitude in the extractive industry is unaffected by their managerial position—high, middle, or low. As a result, H₂ is rejected as upper management does not demonstrate a more environmentally conscious mindset than lower management.

Table 3: ANOVA results for mean difference between EA and managerial positions

Groups	Sum of		Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Squares	df			
Between Groups	.285	2	.142	.716	.490
Within Groups	53.134	267	.199		
Total	53.419	269			

Dependent variable= Environmental attitude (EA)

Source: Researcher 2023

Table 4: Summary of results of the hypotheses tested

Hypothesis	Research method	Data analysis technique	Data source	Test result
H ₁ : A manager's attitude towards the environment is related to his/her firm's corporate reputation.	Survey design	Correlation and GLM	Primary: questionnaire	Accepted
H ₂ : Top level managers exhibit better environmental attitudes than lower level managers.	Survey design	ANOVA	Primary: questionnaire	Rejected

Source: Developed by the Researcher 2023 for the current study

The results show that there is no relationship between company environmental responsibility and financial performance using a small sample of industries. Surprisingly, data showed a favorable association between a number of business environmental accountability measures and financial success indicators. This draws attention to industry specifics and other factors that were not immediately included in the thesis model. Within the context of the CER primary problem, this article sought to investigate the relationship between managers' perceptions of the environment and the corporate reputation of their companies. The results of the test showed a significant correlation between the corporate reputation of the extractive industries and their views toward the environment. To find out

if managers at the top management level had a better environmental attitude than managers at lower management levels, more research was done on the environmental attitudes of managers. The results show that managers, regardless of their position in the administrative hierarchy, have the same environmental attitudes.

Discussion of Findings

The study's first hypothesis (H_1) establishes a positive correlation between a manager's environmental attitudes and the perceived corporate reputation of their company, supported by a statistically significant correlation coefficient of 0.211 at the 1% significance level. This groundbreaking result positions environmental attitude as a significant predictor of corporate reputation, a dimension previously unexplored in academic literature. The finding aligns with Davies et al. (2003), emphasizing that the reputation of firms is influenced by how customer-facing employees perceive the organization. Employees, as noted by Fisher-Buttinger & Vallaster (2008), play a crucial role in shaping corporate reputation, acting as ambassadors who safeguard it and foster goodwill.

This study marks a significant contribution to academia by introducing the correlation between environmental attitude and corporate reputation for the first time. While acknowledging the vital role of employees in reputation building, the literature has been vague about how employees perceive this responsibility. Helm's (2010) research, linking employees' pride and job satisfaction to perceived corporate reputation, underscores the employees' dual role as normative and strategic stakeholders. Their perception of the connection between their environmental attitudes and their company's reputation is deemed critical for steering corporate environmental and reputation management strategies.

However, H_1 , indicating a relationship between environmental attitude and corporate reputation in the extractive sector, leads to the exploration of H_2 , examining top managers' ecological worldviews across three managerial hierarchies: 'manager,' 'senior manager,' and 'executive management.' Surprisingly, the study finds no significant difference in environmental attitudes across these managerial levels, deviating from prior research suggesting a positive correlation between responsible environmental attitudes and upward movement in income and hierarchy.

The study further delves into socio-demographic variables, age, income, education, and political ideology – that have traditionally served as predictors of environmental behavior and attitude. Age is identified as a significant predictor of environmental concern, showing

a decline in environmental concern across age groups since the 1970s. Education demonstrates a positive correlation with environmental knowledge and subsequent behavior, with higher formal education associated with increased pro-environmental behavior. Income, too, emerges as a predictor of responsible environmental behavior, indicating a positive relationship between higher income levels and pro-environmental activities. Political ideology, particularly liberalism, is found to be significantly related to higher environmental concern in various studies.

Unexpectedly, H₂ contradicts established literature, suggesting a departure from the presumed positive relationship between socio-demographic variables and environmental attitudes. The researcher speculates on potential inaccuracies in respondent classification, emphasizing the fluidity in demarcation between managerial positions. The conclusion questions the viability of H₂ in reflecting real-life situations, proposing the need for additional supportive evidence from hypotheses based on income, age, and semi-structured interviews, which were not initially considered in the study.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance is a topic of growing interest and importance in today's business world. Through the analysis of various studies and literature, it is evident that there is a positive relationship between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance. This relationship can be seen through improved brand image and reputation, increased customer loyalty, cost savings through resource efficiency, and enhanced stakeholder engagement. Firstly, companies that prioritize environmental responsibilities are able to improve their brand image and reputation. Consumers and stakeholders are becoming increasingly aware of environmental issues and are more likely to support and engage with companies that demonstrate their commitment to sustainability. This positive perception can result in increased customer loyalty, which in turn has a significant impact on financial performance. A study conducted by Deloitte (2018) found that companies with strong sustainability practices are likely to attract and retain more customers, leading to higher revenues and profits. Secondly, corporate environmental responsibilities can lead to cost savings through resource efficiency. By adopting sustainable practices such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, and water conservation, companies can reduce their operational costs. These cost savings contribute directly to the bottom line and can significantly improve financial performance. A study conducted by Goldman Sachs (2017) revealed that companies that prioritize sustainability achieve higher profit margins compared to their company's peers. Engaging in corporate environmental responsibilities

fosters better stakeholder relationships. Companies that actively involve their stakeholders in their sustainability initiatives are more likely to garner support and cooperation from these parties. This support can translate into various benefits such as access to capital, favorable government policies, and partnerships with other organizations. A study by Eccles et al. (2014) found that companies that engage with stakeholders on environmental sustainability issues experience improved financial performance due to increased access to resources and market opportunities. Additionally, it is important to note that the impact of corporate environmental responsibilities on financial performance may vary across industries and regions. Some industries, such as energy and manufacturing, may face greater scrutiny and regulatory pressures regarding their environmental impacts. Companies in these industries must be proactive in addressing environmental concerns to avoid reputational damage and legal consequences. On the other hand, companies in industries that are less resource-intensive may not face the same level of scrutiny. However, they can still benefit from adopting sustainable practices as it can enhance their competitive advantage and attract environmentally conscious consumers.

Based on the findings and analysis from various studies, several recommendations are made for companies seeking to incorporate corporate environmental responsibilities into their business strategies.

1. **Develop a comprehensive sustainability strategy:** Companies should develop a well-defined and comprehensive sustainability strategy that outlines specific goals, targets, and timelines. This strategy should encompass all aspects of the business and align with the overall corporate objectives. By setting clear objectives, companies can measure their progress and evaluate the impact of their sustainability initiatives on financial performance.
2. **Integrate sustainability into operations and decision-making processes:** Sustainability should not be treated as a separate entity, but rather integrated into the core operations and decision-making processes of the company. This includes incorporating sustainability metrics into performance evaluations and considering environmental impacts when making investment decisions. By embedding sustainability into the fabric of the organization, companies can ensure its long-term performance.
3. **Collaborate with stakeholders:** Companies should actively engage with their stakeholders, including customers, employees, suppliers, and local communities, to foster mutually beneficial relationships. Collaboration can lead to innovative solutions, shared resources, and increased support for sustainability initiatives. By

involving stakeholders in the decision-making process, companies can also ensure that their sustainability efforts are aligned with the expectations and needs of their key stakeholders.

4. Measure and report sustainability performance: Companies should implement robust measurement and reporting systems to track their sustainability performance. This includes monitoring key indicators such as greenhouse gas emissions, energy consumption, waste generation, and water usage. Transparent and credible reporting allows companies to communicate their sustainability achievements to stakeholders, thereby enhancing their brand image and reputation.
5. Stay abreast of evolving regulations and companies standards: Companies need to stay updated on the evolving environmental regulations and companies standards applicable to their operations. Adhering to these regulations not only ensures compliance but also demonstrates a commitment to sustainable practices. By proactively addressing any potential risks or liabilities, companies can protect their financial performance and reputation.

Corporate environmental responsibilities have a positive impact on financial performance through improved brand image and reputation, cost savings through resource efficiency, increased stakeholder engagement, and enhanced customer loyalty. Companies should develop a comprehensive sustainability strategy, integrate sustainability into their operations and decision-making processes, collaborate with stakeholders, measure and report sustainability performance, and stay updated on regulations and companies standards. By addressing environmental responsibilities, companies can not only contribute to a sustainable future but also enhance their competitive advantage and financial performance.

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